

Harmful algal bloom of the dinoflagellate *Blixaea quinquecornis* (Abé) Gottschling in bays of North-Central Peru

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Abstract

Harmful algal blooms of the thecate dinoflagellate, *Blixaea quinquecornis*, generally distributed in tropical, marine, and estuarine areas, are reported in Peru. The identification of this species was done using light, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and differential interference contrast (DIC) microscopy. This species was found in Miraflores, Paracas and Sechura Bays in 2015 and 2016. The maximum density of *B. quinquecornis* observed in Miraflores bay was 3.2×10^5 cells L⁻¹ in summer of 2016. In Paracas Bay, the maximum cell counts were 2.11×10^5 and 4.11×10^4 cells L⁻¹ in the summer and autumn of 2016, respectively. Low cell densities (160 cells L⁻¹) were observed in Sechura Bay. In Miraflores and Paracas Bays, *B. quinquecornis* was found coincidentally with blooms with the athecate dinoflagellate *Akashiwo sanguinea*. The physicochemical variables associated with blooms of *B. quinquecornis* in Miraflores and Paracas Bays were surface sea temperature ranging from 19.9 to 26.6° C, salinities from 34.7 to 35.3, pH from 7.32 to 8.21, and dissolved oxygen from 2.46 to 7.44 mL L⁻¹.

Keywords: Harmful algal bloom, *Blixaea quinquecornis*, dinoflagellates, Miraflores Bay, Paracas Bay, Peru

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Introduction

The thecate dinoflagellate *Blixaea quinquecornis* (Abé, 1927) Gottschling, 2017 (s = *Peridinium quinquecorne*) is primarily a marine species. This species blooms in coastal zones worldwide (Okolodkov *et al.*, 2016) and can reach sufficiently high cell densities to cause both seawater discoloration and fish mortalities (Gárate-Lizárraga and Muñeton-Gómez, 2008). There are few records of this species in South America, although conditions in this region are likely ideal for bloom formation (Rodríguez-Gómez *et al.*, 2021). Existing reports are from the Colombian Caribbean (Lozano-Duque *et al.*, 2011), Brazil (Faust *et al.*, 2005) including this study, has shown that these systems contain abundant dinoflagellate species. Consistent with Margalef's prediction, these habitats are protected from wind mixing, show a high degree of stratification, and have restricted water exchange with surrounding oligotrophic waters of the open barrier-reef system. This limited water exchange favors retention of dinoflagellate cells and the trapping of nutrient rich organic material that is rapidly recycled providing a relatively high-nutrient environment. Species-specific blooms are a common feature of these systems. In the study, the ecology and diversity of dinoflagellate species from two nutrient-enriched habitats, Douglas Cay and The Lair at Twin Cay, were examined in detail. A comparison of the species composition from both sites showed that Douglas Cay contained coastal planktonic and offshore oceanic dinoflagellates while The Lair at Twin Cay contained mainly benthic dinoflagellates. A total of 19 bloom-forming species were observed in these systems during three two-week studies. The morphology of eight of

these bloom-forming species is illustrated in Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM and the Peruvian coasts (Okolodkov *et al.*, 2016).

This study specifically examined the occurrence of *B. quinquecornis* in three bays along the central-north Peruvian coasts. These bays represent a subsection of the Humboldt Current System which impacts the coast of Peru. This system is characterized by a high environmental variability in different spatio-temporal scales, with the presence of temperate-cold waters, strong upwelling, a shallow zone of minimum oxygen (Bertrand *et al.*, 2011), high primary productivity and the occurrence of "El Niño" warm events (Chavez *et al.*, 2008). Harmful algal blooms (HAB) occur frequently in this system. These include recurrent *Akashiwo sanguinea* and *Heterosigma akashiwo* blooms (Sánchez and Delgado, 1996) as well as occasional blooms of *Alexandrium affine* (Vera *et al.*, 1999), *A. minutum* (Baylón *et al.*, 2015), *Pseudo-nitzschia multistriata* (Tenorio *et al.*, 2021), and the non-toxic species, *Azadinium polongum* (Tillmann *et al.*, 2017), among others. In this study, the prevailing environmental conditions associated with observed blooms of *B. quinquecornis* were documented.

Study area

Sechura Bay (Piura) is located north of Peru between 05°12' and 05°50' S, and 80° 50' and 81°12' W. Miraflores Bay (Callao-Lima) is adjacent to Carpayo Beach (fixed station at 12° 04' 09.7" S and 77° 09' 14.4" W), and Paracas Bay (Pisco-Ica) to the south, between 13°47' 2" and 13° 51' 5" S, and 76° 15' 0" - 77° 18' 5" W (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Study area. Sechura bay in the north, a fixed station in Miraflores bay, and Paracas bay in the south. Methods

Surface water samples were collected from Paracas and Miraflores Bays during blooms three times per week from 2015 to 2016, with a bucket and aliquoted into 80 mL bottles. Samples were fixed *in situ* following Thronsen (1978) in Sournia (1978) and Reguera *et al.* (2011). In Sechura Bay, phytoplankton was sampled with a net (10 μm mesh) according to Reguera *et al.* (2011). Surface sea temperature was measured with an immersion mercury thermometer and water samples (250 mL and 100 mL) were collected for salinity, pH, and dissolved oxygen (O_2) analyses. Salinity was measured in laboratory using a salinometer Portasal 8410A and dissolved oxygen was measured following the Winkler method (Strickland and Parsons, 1972). Phytoplankton community quantification was done with using both Zeiss and Leica DMIL LED inverted microscopes with magnifications of 120x and 320x,

following the Utermöhl method, according to Hasle (1978) in Sournia (1978). Algal bloom samples were analyzed in Sedgwick-Rafter chambers (Reguera *et al.*, 2011).

For the identification of *B. quinquecornis*, plate dissection was done, and micrographs were obtained using epifluorescence and DIC-Nomarski techniques. For the epifluorescence microscopy a Nikon Eclipse Ti-U, equipped with an UV lamp Nikon model Intensilight DS-U3 was used with Calcofluor White SM2 stain (Fritz and Triemer, 1985). Microphotographs were taken at 60X using a Nikon model Digital Sight DS-U3 camera. In order to observe the detailed morphology of *B. quinquecornis* specimens, samples were postfixed with Osmium tetroxide, treated for critical point drying and coated with gold for study with SEM (TESCAN model Vega 3) at the “Electronic Microscopy Laboratory, Pathology Institute” (School of Medicine, Nacional de San Marcos University in Lima, Peru).

Morphometry of 40 individual *B. quinquecornis* specimens from the algal bloom in Paracas Bay was done using a light microscope at 40x, and the digital program NIS Element-D, Nikon. Length was considered from the apical to the antapical extremes, with and without spines, and the transdiameter was also measured.

Results

We identified *B. quinquecornis* as the dinoflagellate causing algal blooms in each of the bays. Solitary cells, various chloroplasts per cell and a characteristic reddish eyespot are typical of the species (Fig. 2a). Cells have a conical epitheca and rounded hypotheca,

with four antapical spines (Figs. 2a, e, f). Originally, the plate formula proposed by Abé (1981) is: pp, 3', 2a, 7'', 5c, 4s, 5''', 2'''''. This arrangement is confirmed in this study. Epithecal plates are formed by three apical plates, two anterior intercalary plates and seven precingular plates. Plate 2a is large and has a heptagonal shape, whereas 1a is small and pentagonal (Figs. 2a, b). Measurements of *B. quinquecornis* specimens from Paracas bay had a length of from 19.29 to 27.84 μm ($23.32 \pm 2.25 \mu\text{m}$) and a width (transdiameter) from 14.74 to 23.9 μm (19.34 ± 2.47).

In June 2015 (autumn), *B. quinquecornis* was found in net samples from Sechura Bay at low density, when prevailing environmental conditions were: water temperature 22.7° C; O₂ 2.42 mL L⁻¹; pH 8.57, and salinity 34.50. Cells were also recorded in February 2016 (summer) at densities of ~160 cells L⁻¹, the environmental conditions were: temperature 26.54 °C; O₂ 2.78 mL L⁻¹; pH 7.29; and salinity 34.175. In Paracas Bay, there was an algal bloom caused by *B. quinquecornis* on 23 Feb 2016, having a brownish color and covering a distance of approximately ~3.5 km², with maximal densities of 2.11 x 10⁵ cells L⁻¹, the environmental conditions were: temperature 24.7 °C; O₂ 2.46 mL L⁻¹; pH 7.95; and salinity 35.08. On 25/26 May 2016, the highest density of *B. quinquecornis* observed was 4.11 x 10⁴ cells L⁻¹ (temperature 19.9 °C; O₂ 7.44 mL L⁻¹; pH 8.18, and salinity 35.21). This bloom co-occurred with *A. sanguinea* (1.93 x 10⁵ cells L⁻¹). On the 26 May 2016, the bloom was associated with an especially foul smell, perhaps coming from compounds released by senescing cells. Despite this odor, there were no reports of fish mortalities or human intoxication associated with the bloom.

By Feb 3rd 2016, in Miraflores Bay, densities of *B. quinquecornis* were low (1.96 x 10³ cells L⁻¹), this was related to water warming, with temperature at 25.7° C, a decrease in salinity (34.83), O₂ at 5.17 mL L⁻¹, and pH of 8.21. Three days later *B. quinquecornis* reached a density of 3.2 x 10⁴ cells L⁻¹, corresponding to a temperature of 24.7° C, salinity 35.12 and pH 5.75. This event was previous to another bloom of *A. sanguinea*, which reached densities up to 7 x 10⁶ cells L⁻¹.

Discussion

The dinoflagellate *B. quinquecornis* was identified as the causative species of the algal blooms in the study area. This was mainly based on the cell morphology, particularly the theca tabulation (Abé, 1981; Gottschling *et al.*, 2017). Usually there are four antapical spines according Abé (1927, 1981) and Horiguchi and Pienaar (1991). There is a variant, *P. quinquecorne* var. *trispiniferum*, which differs in having three rigid antapical spines and two small lateral spines (Aké-Castillo and Vázquez, 2011).

Measurements of *B. quinquecornis* cells from Paracas Bay are similar to those provided in other studies from different locations, such as Maribago Bay, the Philippines, reporting a length from 20 - 35.0 μm and a width from 17.5 - 30.0 μm (Horstmann, 1980). In coastal lagoons of Yemen, cells had a length from 21 to 38 μm and width from 17 - 30 μm (Alkawri *et al.*, 2016). In the coasts of Veracruz, Mexico, cells have been reported with a length from 13.5 - 33.9 μm and a width from 12.2 - 29.3 μm (Barón-Campis *et al.*, 2005), and a length from 17.5 - 28.8 μm ($23.22 \pm 2.37 \mu\text{m}$) and a width from 16.3 - 25.0 μm (20.26 ± 2.46) (Okolodkov *et al.*, 2016).

Fig. 2. Morphological details of *Blixaea quinquecornis*, including epithelial plates. a and c) DIC Nomarski technique. b and d). Epifluorescence technique with Calcofluor White. e and f). Ventral view by SEM.

Blixaea quinquecornis is a species related to high temperature. In the Philippines, blooms of this species occur in summer at temperatures between 26 and 28° C and salinities ranging from 35 to 37, although in shallow areas the temperature was 38° C, coinciding with the highest abundance (Horstmann, 1980). Also, in Brazil this species is found at temperatures between 38 and 42° C (Faust *et al.*, 2005), and in Yemen at 33-34° C with a salinity of 36 (Alkawri *et al.*, 2016). The events reported here coincided with an increase of the average temperature (between 19.9 and 24.7° C in Paracas Bay and between 24.7 and 25.7° C in Miraflores Bay), during summer and autumn 2016 when the wind decreased

(Correa *et al.*, 2017), providing favorable conditions for algal bloom formation (Du *et al.*, 2011; Smayda and Trainer, 2010).

Algal blooms caused by *B. quinquecornis* covered relatively small areas in each bay, but cells consistently colored the water dark brown. The highest abundances were found at temperatures between 24.7 and 25.7° C, and salinities between 34.83 and 35.0. The species also occurred in Sechura Bay (bay influenced by tropical currents in summer) and probably in other areas of the Peruvian coast. These findings are important considering the tendency of the temperature to increase as a consequence of climate change, therefore favoring new HAB events and the expansion of niches for invasive species (Gobler *et al.*, 2017) yet the impacts of such changes on harmful algal blooms (HABs).

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